

Implementing participatory approaches in the French dairy sector

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Dairy cow sector

Dairy cattle

The French Dairy Cattle meeting gathered 26 attendees of 8 types of organizations (farmers, veterinarians, health advisors). The goal was to work from results obtained in 2 other projects: IdEA, in which an approach to reduce AMU was created; and UniFilAnim Santé, in which the setting up of participatory meetings between breeders and vets was tested to improve herd health management. The interest of these approaches having been approved, it was henceforth necessary to find solutions to perpetuate them. Thus, breeders and advisers were gathered during a webinar, following which the results were deepened by contacting other professionals. This was held during 6 months in 2021-2022.

The strategy tested in the Living Lab

During the IdEA projects (which aimed to promote co-construction between breeders and veterinarians of an action plan to reduce AMU on farm level) and UniFilAnim Santé (which aimed to develop the organization of participatory meetings between breeders and health experts), a real interest from professionals had been shown concerning the usefulness of these participatory approaches, but the main obstacle to their implementation was economic. The meeting's strategy was therefore to find out whether other professionals from different organizations would be interested in these approaches and, if so, what solutions would they consider making them permanent. The "webinar" format permitted to bring together a greater number of people to obtain a greater diversity of points of view.

The roadmap to implementation

During the webinar, 2 existing groups from the 2 previous projects (IdEA and UniFilAnim Santé) were merged into the group. Results of WP1 of Roadmap, the IdEA and UniFilAnim Santé approaches were presented. Sub-working groups were then organized to discuss sustainability solutions. The participants showed real interest in the results and provided solutions. We had planned to organize 2 other webinars to deepen the solutions for each of the projects, but the partners of IdEA first wanted to obtain data on the impact of the approach before continuing the sustainability and, for UniFilAnim, the solutions provided and their deepening through contact with other professionals after the webinar showed that only training funds could respond to the problem. So, for this project, it was not necessary to bring the participants together again because only one solution exists and its implementation is governed by an established protocol.

The impact created by the Living Lab

- Animal Health and AMU: The main impact was to observe that the breeders as well as the advisers are motivated to create more dialogue, more inter-knowledge during participatory meetings or during co-construction of a cattle health approach. Constructive communication between breeders and with advisors seems to be an expected and effective lever for improving herd health and reducing AMU. Offering stakeholders training in counseling pedagogy including the 2 presented approaches would be a first step.
- Costs and savings: However, breeders don't want to incur additional costs to participate in these long-term approaches. It is therefore necessary to find financial aids, but the solutions are limited.

Vendredi 1^{er} octobre – Visioconférence De 13h à 14h30

ROADMAP, UnifilAnim Santé et IdEA sont trois projets complémentaires qui portent sur la gestion de la santé des animaux d'élevage et la réduction de l'utilisation des antibiotiques (cf pièce jointe). ROADMAP est un projet à portée européenne tandis que les deux autres projets sont régionaux (UnifilAnim Santé en Pays de la Loire et IdEA en Normandie). Vous avez participé ou vous participez à l'un d'entre eux.

Nous vous invitons à un moment de partage de résultats et de discussion autour de la question de l'utilisation prudente des antibiotiques en élevage bovin lait le 1er octobre prochain, de 13h à 14h30.

Tous les acteurs concernés par cette problématique (éleveurs, techniciens, vétérinaires...) en Bretagne, Pays de la Loire et Normandie sont conviés. Ce sera donc l'occasion d'échanger entre acteurs de la santé de différentes régions.

Cette réunion se fera **en visioconférence** pendant 1h30 et se déclinera en plusieurs parties :

1. Les résultats des projets
2. Deux témoignages d'acteurs de terrain impliqués dans les projets : un éleveur et un vétérinaire qui ont mis en place la démarche d'accompagnement IDEEA sur la gestion de la santé, et un vétérinaire impliqué dans UNIFILANIM
3. Echanges autour des démarches présentées
4. Et pour la suite, comment pérenniser ces démarches ?

Voici le lien pour vous inscrire : <https://framaforms.org/inscription-a-la-reunion-dechanges-sur-lutilisation-prudente-des-antibiotiques-1629721599>

Le lien de connexion vous sera envoyé quelques jours avant la visio-conférence.

Nous vous attendons nombreux pour cet échange qui contribuera à faire avancer les problématiques autour de l'utilisation prudente des antibiotiques en élevage à l'échelle européenne !

L'équipe des projets ROADMAP, UnifilAnim Santé et IdEA.

Challenges

- Bring farmers and advisers together in a webinar on a project they don't know
- Presented a lot of results and have sufficient time to discuss in 1h30
- Find a wide range of solutions for the sustainability of the approaches
- The will of the partners of the IdEA project not to continue for the moment

Successes

- Many professionals in the sector were interested in the subject
- The desire to create dialogue between breeders and between breeders and advisers
- The desire to have a global approach to herd health

In order to reduce the use of antibiotics, a systemic approach of the herd is essential, as well as mutual knowledge between the stakeholders and taking into account the needs of each. This requires time, therefore funding, that could be found through training funds to set up participatory meetings.

www.roadmap-h2020.eu

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